

Tracking the Pulse of the Ocean

Gaps in BGC EOVs identified to justify proposed updates - Assessment of current (2017) BGC EOVS Specification Sheets

Milestone number: MS8

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1 Executive summary

The BioGeoSea project aims to enhance the observation, integration and use of Biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables (BGC EOVs) to better monitor ocean health, support climate assessments, and deliver societally relevant indicators. A key component of this effort is the revision of the EOV requirements and Specification Sheets (Spec Sheets), which reinforce the design and implementation of the global ocean observing systems.

Within this context, Milestone MS8 provides a gap assessment of the current BGC EOV Spec Sheets, most of which were developed mainly in 2017 and have since played an important role in guiding the implementation of sustained biogeochemical observations within the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), by defining the scientific basis, measurement approaches, observing networks, and data management structures needed to support a standardized global monitoring of ocean biogeochemistry. The scientific, technological, and policy developments over the past decade require a systematic revision of the Spec Sheets to ensure they remain aligned with actual observing capabilities, international requirements frameworks, and societal priorities. This assessment identifies several gaps:

First, the existing Specification Sheets show structural inconsistencies and incomplete information is present across several sections. Key elements such as uncertainty requirements, spatial/vertical coverage, and the link between observing requirements and existing observing systems are often missing or unclear. As a result, the Spec Sheets do not function as an operational guidance for observing system design;

Second, significant technological progress has occurred since the Spec Sheets were developed. Advances in autonomous platforms (e.g., BGC-Argo), sensor technologies, machine learning based bias correction, and satellite observations, have expanded potentials of the observing capacity for several BGC EOVs, but this progress is not reflected in the current Spec Sheets.

Third, alignments with international frameworks remain insufficient. The current Spec Sheets are not fully harmonized with GOOS EOV endorsement process, the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) Rolling Review of Requirements (RRR), and the GCOS requirements for Essential Climate Variables (ECVs). Harmonization with, and acknowledgement of these frameworks is required to ensure consistency in terminology, readiness levels assessments, and uncertainty definitions, as well as to inform end users of the complexity of the requirements landscape.

Fourth, data management and best practices are not well addressed. The current Spec Sheets provide limited guidance on data flow i.e., EOV data schema: data submission pipeline (standards → data system → application), metadata standards, FAIR principles, and links to best practices.

Finally, societal and policy relevance are not sufficiently expressed. The role of BGC observations in supporting climate mitigation and adaptation, biodiversity monitoring, and international policy frameworks is not clearly reflected.

For these reasons, a coordinated update of all BGC EOVS Spec Sheets is undertaken. In this BioGeoSea Milestone, we identify structural and content gaps in all Spec Sheets for BGC EOVS pointing to different specific update needs, across the observing value chain.

Our gap assessment will significantly help the development of updated and harmonized Spec Sheets. The next phase will involve consultations with identified stakeholders and end users to refine requirements and further strengthen the fitness for purpose of EOVS Spec Sheets, setting a foundation for the long-term sustainability of global BGC ocean observations.

2 Introduction

BioGeoSea aims to strengthen the observation, integration, and use of the Biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables (BGC EOVS) to better monitor ocean health, support climate assessments, and develop societally relevant indicators. A key part of this effort is revising the current EOVS requirements and Specification Sheets, which guide the design and implementation of global ocean observing systems. In line with this objective, BioGeoSea's Milestone 8 presents the gap assessment of the 2017 Specification Sheets (Spec Sheets) for the biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables (BGC EOVS).

These Spec Sheets play an important role in guiding the implementation of the global observations by defining the scientific interest, observing requirements, observations approaches, and data management pathways associated with each EOVS. Their main objective is to support the generation of globally comparable and interoperable observations, allowing data collected by different operators, platforms and observing systems to be combined into a coherent global dataset.

To fulfill this, the Spec Sheets must provide clear and up-to-date guidance on how observations should be carried out, validated, managed, and delivered to end users. However, the current version of the BGC EOVS Spec Sheets was developed several years ago (2017), and important developments have occurred since then in observing technologies, methods, data management plans, and observing networks. A systematic review and update is required to assure that the existing Spec Sheets remain fit-for-purpose.

The aim of this milestone is to evaluate and assess the current Spec Sheets and identify gaps that limit their effectiveness. The assessment focuses on determining whether the Spec Sheets are up to date, whether they can be readily used by operators, and how efficiently they support the generation of standardized measurements.

This gap assessment covers the Spec Sheets of nine BGC EOVS currently defined within GOOS: Oxygen, Nutrients, Inorganic Carbon, Transient Tracers, Particulate Matter, Nitrous Oxide, Stable Carbon Isotopes, Dissolved Organic Carbon, and Ocean Colour.

For each EOVS, the Spec Sheets was reviewed to evaluate its completeness, consistency, and alignment with current observing capabilities.

By identifying these gaps, this document aims to provide updated content and structure to the new version of the Spec Sheets, in order to increase their utility.

Some sections of the milestone intentionally repeat similar, or even identical gaps across different EOVs. This is done to facilitate the review process, as each EOV Spec Sheet will be revised and updated independently by a dedicated group of contributors led by two expert Lead Authors.

This milestone reflects the current state of the gap assessment at the time of submission. Feedback from community received after its publication will be collected and considered in subsequent activities, particularly in the revision of the Spec Sheets.

3 Gaps in EOV Specification Sheets

3.1 Oxygen

BGC EOV Oxygen Specification Sheet (Version: 2017.08.25)

GOOS+IOCCP (2017): https://www.ioccp.org/images/10FOO/BGC-EOV-Spec-Sheets_Aug-2017/01-EOV-BGC_Oxygen_20170825.pdf

The Oxygen EOV Spec Sheet provides a helpful baseline but is now outdated (technology, networks, products) and under-specified in key areas for compliance of fitness for purpose, including uncertainty, drift, coastal hypoxia observing design, and end-to-end data flow.

Table 1. Oxygen EOV Spec Sheet section-by-section gap assessments

Section	Gap/ Comment
Background and justification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are no references; the section does not reflect post-2017 progress in autonomous dissolved oxygen observations and synthesis products. • Expansion on societal drivers within the EOV specific description would be useful. • Update on the importance and impact of dissolved oxygen post-2017 is required. • There is no mention of the biological, economic, or societal implications of global oxygen loss, which motivate calls for expanded observing capacity and coverage. • No mention of term "deoxygenation" in section. • Addition of sentence distinguishing between eutrophication-driven oxygen loss in coastal zones and global deoxygenation could be valuable. • This section could be organized as: causes, observing and measuring, trends versus variability, data model discrepancy, regional and local settings, and impacts.
Table 1: EOV information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Missing definition of AOU, NCP, net carbon export flux, Pressure needed also. • Missing units of the sub-variable (mg/L, % saturation, $\mu\text{mol/kg}$, $\mu\text{mol/L}$, etc.).

Section	Gap/ Comment
Table 2: Requirement's settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific applications and drivers should be summarized in the background (currently in a table). • Readiness level is not explained: for funders and non-GOOS readers, they won't know what that means. • The eutrophication column is empty (temporal scale, spatial scale, magnitude is missing). • Guidance on temporal scale of the phenomena is not explicit (e.g., what 'weekly to monthly' means operationally across platforms). • The phenomena list is incomplete: oxygen is linked to more than four phenomena (e.g., export fluxes, and carbon sequestration). • The uncertainty discussion is too brief, there are missing references and information about sensor accuracy, drift, calibration, etc. Target uncertainty could be replaced by recommended quality (see Table 2 in Grégoire et al., 2021). • Missing small spatiotemporal scale phenomena (hypoxic events, fish kills, algae blooms, etc).
Figure 1: Spatial and temporal scales of phenomena	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure 2 duplicates table 2 without adding interpretation, so these two rows : temporal and spatial scales could be omitted and, in the Figure, we would write on each ellipse the phenomena. • Does not distinguish between "coastal" and "open ocean" for Phenomena 2. • Should be completed considering the full list of phenomena to be considered.
Table 3: Current 2017 observing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Table 3 content reflects the 2017 state; it forgets consolidated observing networks (especially autonomous networks). • Sensor accuracy/uncertainty is presented as fixed numbers without context (conditions, drift, calibration). • Accuracy, precision and measurement uncertainty are not defined (for instance, uncertainty defined here as the standard deviation of the measured O₂ concentration compared to a standard reference value (mostly Winkler) (see Table 4 Grégoire et al., 2021). May also need to be provided in different units other than μmol/kg as a variety is used across deoxygenation field (oceanographers vs biologists vs modelers). • Table 3 mixes approach readiness with observing network readiness but does not explain the logic. Provide the rationale. • Some links are not working: OceanSITES; OceanGliders. • <u>Moored fixed-point observatories should address the "coastal"</u> (i.e., very nearshore or estuarine) aspects of Phenomena 2, but this is not listed currently. Additional links to any nearshore coastal observing systems measuring O₂ should be added if available. • <u>Vertical coverage</u> missing from all.

Section	Gap/ Comment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Readiness level</u> again not defined here; nor difference between readiness level of approach vs observing system. • <u>Reporting mechanisms section</u> not currently useful. • <u>Profiling float footprint</u> empty, though Figure 2 has an ellipse that suggests we have this information.
Table 4: Future observing capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Currently “not defined”; to be verified with experts, we could add AniBOS, citizen science networks. • Major post-2017 developments are not represented (expanded autonomous observing, improved quality control (QC) and quality flag (QF) approaches, data-drives bias correction).
Figure 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the caption mention of thin back circles (for Table 4), Table 4 being empty. • Largely repeats Table 3 content without adding interpretation.
Table 5: Data and information creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and information creation is largely incomplete. • Lists repositories but not integration architecture: Data flow: Platform→QC→synthesis→indicator is not described or indication of a reference. • Metadata information missing. • Some links are not working: Ifremer Coriolis, OceanSITES, Ocean-Gliders,
Table 6: Links and references	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citations needs updating . • Connection to Ocean Best practices Systems(OBPS) is needed.
Glossary of terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Terminology and indicators should be defined according to GOOS vocabulary. The current terminology list dates from 2017 and may require revision to reflect updated conventions. • The updated Spec Sheet could help standardize variable names across observing systems. For example, different naming conventions are currently used in datasets such as The Global Ocean Data Analysis Project (GLODAP) and Biogeochemical Argo (BGC- Argo) (e.g., DOXY/CTDOXY/OXYGEN), and metadata harmonization would improve interoperability and data integration.
List of abbreviations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The terminology may need to be revised, as the current list dates from 2017.

General gaps:

- Many of these gaps can be alleviated (hopefully) by using Grégoire et al. (2021) and Garçon et al., (2026).
- Trend detectability and drift requirements are missing: if the EOVS is meant to detect decadal deoxygenation, the Spec Sheet could define detectability targets and operational drift tolerance.

- Vertical resolution and deep ocean requirements are under-specified: Oxycline/Oxygen Minimum Zone boundaries and deep dissolved oxygen changes require explicit vertical sampling guidance.
- Coastal hypoxia design is not operationalized: the Spec Sheet acknowledges hypoxic regions but does not explain what is the minimum observing density.
- Coastal hypoxia is not operationalized: the Spec Sheets acknowledge hypoxic regions but do not define standardized thresholds (e.g., for hypoxia) or specify the observing requirements needed to monitor them.
- Information about the lead authors and contributors of each Spec Sheet is missing and should be provided.
- Discussion of preferred units for measurements of dissolved oxygen could be added here.

3.2 Nutrients

BGC EOV Nutrients Specification Sheet (Version: 2017.08.25)

GOOS+IOCCP (2017): https://www.ioccp.org/images/10FOO/BGC-EOV-Spec-Sheets_Aug-2017/02-EOV-BGC_Nutrients_20170825.pdf

Table 2. Nutrients EOV Spec Sheet section-by-section gap assessments

Section	Gap/ Comment
Background and justification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No reference is provided in this section, and the content should be updated to reflect post-2017 developments. • Expanding the discussion on societal drivers would strengthen the section. • An updated description of the importance and impacts of dissolved inorganic nutrients is needed. It should also clarify that not all nutrient forms are included (e.g., DON and DOP are not considered). • Need to update list of macronutrients to NH_4^+, NO_2^-, SiOH_4^{4-}, PO_4^{3-}, NO_3^- and be consistent throughout the whole document. • In the introduction, we mention the 5 nutrients, however, the rest of the document only mentions 3. We should add an explanation of why that is.
Table 1: EOVI information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The derived products list is incomplete and vaguely defined. It is unclear how derived products are specified and whether products such as ecosystem health indicators, biological carbon pump metrics, stoichiometric ratios, or biological uptake and drawdown should be explicitly included. • There is no clear link between sub-variables and phenomena. • A link to derived product definition and supporting variable definition (such as defined by GOOS) would be useful.

Section	Gap/ Comment
Table 2a: Requirement's settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incomplete requirement fields: several cells are blank (temporal scaled, spatial scales, magnitudes, current and target uncertainty) especially for deoxygenation, land-sea fluxes, and benthic fluxes. • Target uncertainty is not specified. It is unclear whether this refers to measurement uncertainty (e.g., analytical precision) or uncertainty relative to the observed signal (i.e., the ability to resolve the phenomenon). • Temporal resolution is described using broad categories(e.g., annual/decadal, seasonal/decadal, sub-weekly/decadal) but does not define minimum sampling frequency or trend detection thresholds. The distinction between coastal and open ocean sampling requirements should also be clearly indicated, as coastal waters are commonly more dynamic and require higher sampling frequency. • For all phenomena, there is no indication about Current Uncertainty Relative to the Signal and Target Uncertainty Relative to the Signal. • Other list of phenomena to capture (i.e., Deoxygenation, Land-sea fluxes, Benthic fluxes) are missing information about temporal, spatial scales and uncertainty. • In readiness level of the observing network: fixed-point observatories are missing; the approach is labeled mature but the observing network readiness is not specified.
Figure 1: Spatial and temporal scales of phenomena	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incomplete representation of the phenomena: Some phenomena from Table 2 are missing (i.e., remineralization, Deoxygenation, Land-sea fluxes, Benthic fluxes). • Caption incomplete (can refer to table 2 but also need to list the phenomena associated to each colour. Technically we should not have to go back to the text/paper to understand the figure).
Table 3: Current 2017 observing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An update of the readiness level of the observing approach (i.e., profiling float is no longer Pilot) is needed. • The leading observing network related to ship-based fixed-point observatories is missing. There is no named network for fixed-point observatories (e.g., OceanSites). The table leaves this cell blank, although the approach is marked as Mature. • Under spatial scale currently captured: for fixed-point observatories, vertical coverage is missing, same for profiling floats, for which nutrient vertical resolution is critical (i.e., nitracline detection, remineralization gradients, etc.). • Footprint is undefined everywhere. • Typical Observing Frequency for profiling floats is missing. No known frequency is specified (i.e., float cycle time 5 to 10 days). • The "supporting variables measured" section is complete for ship-based approaches but remains incomplete for profiling

Section	Gap/ Comment
	<p>floats. For example, floats typically measure temperature and salinity, but this is not specified.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For ship based repeat hydrography, supporting variables are measured over the full water column, not only at the surface and sub-surface, and this should be clearly stated. • For profiling floats, the vertical coverage of supporting variables should be specified (e.g., Argo profiles typically extend to 2000m. • References about accuracy and uncertainty should be added/ updated. The numbers provided should also mention if it's the accuracy or the uncertainty on the measurement.
Table 4: Future observing capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The link to the Glider observing network is no longer active. • This section can be merged to table 3.
Figure 2: Spatial and temporal observation scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The figure largely reproduces information in Table 3 content without adding interpretation. • Consider enhancing the figure by including a third dimension (e.g., depth) to better represent vertical coverage and improve readability.
Table 5: Data and information creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data product specification related to which observing approach they integrated is unclear (e.g., GLODAP uses only ship-based bottle data). • Repositories are listed, but the pathway: Platform →QC→synthesis→indicator is not described.
Table 6: Links and references	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latest references date from 2016: given the evolution in autonomous UV nitrate sensors, intercalibration exercises and global and regional data products, this list needs revision.
Glossary of terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The current terminology list dates from 2017 and may require revision to reflect updated conventions. • Glossary of terms would benefit from links to stand. Metadata for example acronyms like in e.g., GLODAP: NITRAT/NITRIT/PHSPHT/SILCAT and other relevant naming conventions.
List of abbreviations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The terminology may need to be revised, as the current list dates from 2017.

General gaps:

- Missing requirements.
- Overall table 3 does not define what is sufficient? What is required? And what is missing relative to table 2 requirements?
- While classified as mature, the nutrients EOVS Spec Sheet lacks quantitative uncertainty targets, incomplete requirement definitions for several phenomena, and does not reconcile precision difference between ship-based (i.e., $0.03 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) and autonomous platform observations ($0.5\text{--}3.0 \mu\text{M}$) for nitrate.

- Information about the lead authors and contributors of each Spec Sheet is missing and should be provided.

3.3 Inorganic Carbon

BGC EOVS Inorganic Carbon Specification Sheet (Version: 2017.08.25)

GOOS+IOCCP(2017): https://www.ioccp.org/images/10FOO/BGC-EOV-Spec-Sheets_Aug-2017/03-EOV-BGC_Inorganic-Carbon_20170825.pdf

Table 3. Inorganic Carbon EOVS Spec Sheet section-by-section gap assessments

Section	Gap/ Comment
Background and justification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no reference and no explicit information about why this EOVS matters to policy agreements and context related to ocean acidification monitoring frameworks. • There is no differentiation between coastal versus open ocean observation differences (i.e., information about impact into societal interest/ risk need to be added). • An updated description of the importance and impacts of inorganic carbon is needed.
Table 1: EOVS information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sub-variables: Does not explain priority combinations for different application/phenomena: e.g., acidification indicators: TA+DIC or TA+pH maybe a small matrix: phenomena → minimum variables recommended.
Table 2: Requirement's settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current uncertainty relative to signal row is blank across phenomena. Only target uncertainty appears for three phenomena. • Target uncertainty is missing for primary productivity (phenomena 4) and export fluxes (phenomena 5) → table 2 is incomplete and requires revision.
Figure 1: Spatial and temporal scales of phenomena	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure 1 is a visualization of table 2. It does not add interpretive value beyond the table.
Table 3: Current 2017 observing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are multiple missing cells and inconsistencies. • <u>The leading observing network</u> is blank for drifters and ship-based fixed-point observatories. • The link to the OceanSites is no longer working. • <u>Spatial scales</u> currently captured have missing horizontal/vertical coverage fields. • <u>Sensor/technique and accuracy section</u> variety of sensors are being developed without naming types for float-based $p\text{CO}_2$ /DIC/TA.

Section	Gap/ Comment
Table 4: Future observing capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Check of units for TA/DIC accuracy in table 4 is needed. • "How does this novel aspect impact our observing capacity?" row in empty. • "Time-Scale Until Part of Observing System" row is empty. • "Supporting Variables Measured" row is empty.
Figure 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure 2 is a visualization of table 3. It does not add interpretive value beyond the table.
Table 5: Data and information creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Table 5 is incomplete for several approaches: Moored-fixed-point observatories: missing QC, Near Real Time (NRT) delivery, products (partially filled). • Drifters: entirely blank. • Ship-based fixed-point observatories: mostly blank. • Many links are old and may be stale. • Reference to regional data products is missing.
Table 6: Links and references	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many links appear outdated and may no longer be active; an update with more recent references is required.
Glossary of terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The current terminology list dates from 2017 and may require revision to reflect updated conventions and terminology used in recent datasets and observing programs. • Acronyms for data variables are not standardized across datasets (e.g., TCARBN/ ALKALI/ PH_TOT_25C /PH) harmonizing these naming conventions would improve consistency and interoperability.
List of abbreviations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The terminology may need to be revised, as the current list dates from 2017.
List of references	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This section is empty; relevant references should be included in the Specification Sheet.

General gaps:

- Requirement table is incomplete: current uncertainties are not stated and target uncertainties are missing for primary production and export fluxes.
- Table 3 is missing critical observing: leading networks absent for drifters and well-established observation systems such as the integrated carbon observation system ([ICOS](#)).
- Information about the lead authors and contributors of each Spec Sheet is missing and should be provided.

3.4 Transient Tracers

BGC EOV Transient Tracers Specification Sheet ((Version: 2017.08.25))

GOOS+IOCCP(2017): https://www.ioccp.org/images/10FOO/BGC-EOV-Spec-Sheets_Aug-2017/04-EOV-BGC_Transient-Tracers_20170825.pdf

Table 4. Transient Tracers EOVSPEC Sheet section-by-section gap assessments

Section	Gap/ Comment
Background and justification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The text lacks a societal framing. While it explains the scientific relevance, it does not clearly link the observations to climate mitigation, policy reporting or decision-making needs. An updated description of the importance and impacts of transient tracers is needed.
Table 1: EOVSPEC information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The section is well defined; however, an update is needed since the information dates from 2017 and does not incorporate more recent developments.
Table 2: Requirement's settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This section is concise and appears complete; however, an update is needed to reflect developments after 2017 The "Current uncertainty relative to signal" is blank, and not quantified. The Target uncertainty is stated but not justified or explained. The magnitude of anthropogenic carbon sequestration magnitude is unclear; it is not specified whether it refers to total global storage or annual increment, etc.
Figure 1: Spatial and temporal scales of phenomena	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Figure 1 adds minimal interpretive value beyond Table 2 and does not indicate platform-phenomena matching.
Table 3: Current 2017 observing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only one observing approach is listed. Vertical coverage should state fill depth. Footprint is not defined. Observing frequency: is vague because Go-SHIP sections are typically decadal. Measurement and accuracy section: no reference about uncertainty estimate.
Table 4: Future observing capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Allows better quantification": should quantify how it improves age resolution.
Figure 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Figure 2 is a visualization of table 3 . It does not add interpretive value beyond the table.
Table 5: Data and information creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Near real-time data stream delivery column is blank: possibly appropriate, but should explicitly state: 'no NRT data stream delivery'. No information about : how long after cruise until product availability?
Table 6: Links and references	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Many links are old and may be stale→ links should be updated.
Glossary of terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The current terminology list dates from 2017 and may require revision to reflect updated conventions.

List of abbreviations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The terminology may need to be revised, as the current list dates from 2017.
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General gap:

- Information about the lead authors and contributors of each Spec Sheet is missing and should be provided.

3.5 Particulate Matter

BGC EOVS Particulate Matter Specification Sheet (Version: 2017.08.25)

GOOS+IOCCP (2017): https://www.ioccp.org/images/10FOO/BGC-EOV-Spec-Sheets_Aug-2017/05-EOV-BGC_Part particulate-Matter_20170825.pdf

Table 5. Particulate Matter EOVS Spec Sheet section-by-section gap assessments

Section	Gap/ Comment
Background and justification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is no reference; the section does not reflect post-2017 progress. Expanding on societal drivers with EOVS specific description would be more useful. The Spec Sheet does not clearly state what the core EOVS variable and what are the derived products. Although impacts on fisheries and water quality are mentioned, there is no structured link to: Carbon budget assessment, ecosystem monitoring frameworks. An updated description of the importance and impacts of Particulate Matter is needed.
Table 1: EOVS information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The sub-variable section combines state variables, flux variables, and biogeochemical tracers; it is unclear whether this is intentional. The "derived products" row is empty and should be completed. The list of supporting variables does not clarify which variables are mandatory or contextual.
Table 2: Requirement's settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The "Current uncertainty" row is blank and should be quantified. Magnitude definitions are inconsistent: units vary between concentration, decadal rate, and annual rate expressed in decadal units. The remineralization column is incomplete, despite remineralization being a central process of the biological pump.
Figure 1: Spatial and temporal scales of phenomena	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Figure 1 visualizes overlapping phenomena, but it adds limited interpretative value beyond the information already presented in table 2 and does not link the phenomena to observing platforms used.

Section	Gap/ Comment
Table 3: Current 2017 observing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vertical coverage is missing for most observing approaches. Footprint is undefined everywhere. Leading observing network links should be updated. Accuracy/uncertainty not quantified: no numerical values given, that is insufficient for a specification sheet. Leading observing network missing for some approaches.
Table 4: Future observing capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time-Scale field is blank and need should be completed, if the information is not available, it should explicitly state "not defined". The accuracy/uncertainty estimate field is blank and no values are provided. All future elements are labeled "concept"; an update is needed to reflect developments since 2017.
Figure 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The note "Spec Sheets not visualized because no temporal or spatial scale was provided" indicates incomplete specification of the observational requirements.
Table 5: Data and information creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The section on Moored fixed-point observatories is largely incomplete. The section on optical imaging systems is blank. The section on gliders is mostly blank. No unified particulate matter product derived from observations is identified.
Table 6: Links and references	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information about best practices and guides is blank.
Glossary of terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The current terminology list dates from 2017 and may require revision to reflect updated conventions.
List of abbreviations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The terminology may need to be revised, as the current list dates from 2017.

General gaps:

- Derived products files empty (Table1).
- Current uncertainty (2017) relative to signal is not specified (Table 2).
- Remineralization column incomplete (Table 2).
- Vertical coverage and footprint are undefined across platforms (Table 3).
- Accuracy/uncertainty values not quantified (Table 3).
- There is no statement about sampling density requirement, how remote sensing and in-situ observations integrate quantitatively?
- Information about the lead authors and contributors of each Spec Sheet is missing and should be provided.

3.6 Nitrous Oxide

BGC EOVS Nitrous Oxide Specification Sheet (Version: 2017.08.25)

GOOS+IOCCP (2017): https://www.ioccp.org/images/10FOO/BGC-EOV-Spec-Sheets_Aug-2017/06-EOV-BGC_Nitrous-Oxide_20170825.pdf

Table 6. Nitrous Oxide EOV Spec Sheet section-by-section gap assessments

Section	Gap/ Comment
Background and justification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This section is scientifically solid and well framed. Needs addition if CH₄ is added to the EOV, as discussed over a few years.
Table 1: EOV information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is no specification of which of Nitrous oxide (N₂O) variables are of interest: interior ocean N₂O, or N₂O air-sea flux. Supporting variables list need revision for example including dissolved oxygen, nitrate, ammonium, mixed layer depth, wind speed (for flux calculation).
Table 2: Requirement's settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The magnitude/range of signal is unclear. The meaning of "increase of nitrogen" is unclear and requires clarification. The "Current uncertainty relative to signal" field is empty. Requirements for phenomena "air-sea fluxes" are not specified in sufficient detail.
Figure 1: Spatial and temporal scales of phenomena	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Figure 1 does not represent air-sea flux and does not connect phenomena to observing networks.
Table 3: Current 2017 observing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vertical coverage is not defined. Footprint is not specified. Spatial coverage is incomplete and requires clarification.
Table 4: Future observing capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The "phenomena addressed" is empty: given N₂O relevance to air-sea flux and upwelling, this should be specified. "How does this novel aspect impact our observing capacity?" not filled. This weakens clarity and efficiency of the Spec Sheet.
Figure 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Figure 2 is a visualization of table 3 and table 4. It does not add interpretive value beyond both tables.
Table 5: Data and information creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Many links are old and may be stale. Data access restricted: MEMENTO (available only upon free registration). This conflicts with open-data principles of GOOS. NRT data stream column largely blank.
Table 6: Links and references	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information about best practices and methodological guides is missing. Several links appear outdated and should be updated.
Glossary of terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The current terminology list dates from 2017 and may require revision to reflect updated conventions.

Section	Gap/ Comment
List of abbreviations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The terminology may need to be revised, as the current list dates from 2017.

General gaps:

- No clear operational boundary of the EOV (concentration versus flux).
- Supporting variables are missing.
- Current and targeted uncertainties relative to signal not defined (Table 2).
- Vertical coverage and footprint not specified (Table 3).
- Data access partially restricted.
- Information about the lead authors and contributors of each Spec Sheet is missing and should be provided.
- Currently no agreed-upon SOPs.
- No reference materials for discrete samples.
- Might require regional boundaries as EOV (in other words, it might not be necessary to cover CH₄ in offshore regions, potentially also true for N₂O).

3.7 Stable Carbon Isotopes

BGC EOV Stable Carbon Isotopes Specification Sheet (Version: 2017.08.25)

GOOS+IOCCP (2017): https://www.ioccp.org/images/10FOO/BGC-EOV-Spec-Sheets_Aug-2017/07-EOV-BGC_Stable-Carbon-Isotopes_20170825.pdf

Table 7. Stable Carbon Isotopes EOV Spec Sheet section-by-section gap assessments

Section	Gap/ Comment
Background and justification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is no reference; Limited societal framing in the background section. An updated description of the importance and impacts of stable carbon isotopes is needed.
Table 1: EOV information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An update is needed for the revised version of the Spec Sheet.
Table 2: Requirement's settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The readiness level is indicated as "mature", but the readiness of the observing networks differs across approaches (see table 3). The magnitude/range of the signal is incomplete for air-sea fluxes (phenomena 3). Units are inconsistent (annual vs decadal). The current uncertainty relative to signal" field is empty.
Figure 1: Spatial and temporal scales of phenomena	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Figure 2 reproduces information from table 2. It does not add interpretation. The air-sea flux phenomena are not visually represented in the figure.
Table 3: Current 2017 observing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For all three observing approaches, the vertical coverage field is left blank. However, for isotope-based anthropogenic carbon estimation, full-depth coverage is essential.

Section	Gap/ Comment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The footprint associated with spatial scale is not specified.
Table 4: Future observing capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This section should be updated to include any technological developments that have emerged since 2017.
Figure 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Figure 2 is a visualization of table 3. It does not add interpretive value beyond the table.
Table 5: Data and information creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The list of data products has not been updated since 2016 and should be reviewed and verified. The "near real time data stream delivery" is empty. Since this type of EOV may not support NRT delivery, this should be explicitly stated.
Table 6: Links and references	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Several links appear outdated and references should be updated.
Glossary of terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The current terminology list dates from 2017 and may require revision to reflect updated conventions.
List of abbreviations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The terminology may need to be revised, as the current list dates from 2017.

General gaps:

- Vertical coverage and footprint are not defined.
- The list of data products needs to be updated.
- Information about the lead authors and contributors of each Spec Sheet is missing and should be provided.

3.8 Dissolved Organic Carbon

BGC EOV Dissolved Organic Carbon Specification Sheet (Version: 2017.08.25)

GOOS+IOCCP (2017): https://www.ioccp.org/images/10FOO/BGC-EOV-Spec-Sheets_Aug-2017/08-EOV-BGC_Dissolved-Organic-Carbon_20170825.pdf

Table 8. Dissolved Organic Carbon EOV Spec Sheet section-by-section gap assessments

Section	Gap/ Comment
Background and justification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The operational scope remains implicit, and there is no indication about the societal drivers behind maintaining long-term observing system of the EOV (e.g., climate, ecosystem health). An updated description of the importance (i.e., role) and global impacts of dissolved organic carbon is needed.
Table 1: EOV information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An update is needed for the revised version of the Spec Sheet. Consider temporal/spatial differences in DOC. Links to supporting variables could be more explicitly described.

Section	Gap/ Comment
Table 2: Requirement's settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The "current uncertainty" row is empty, and no reference is provided to justify the target uncertainty. • The temporal scale for remineralization is vaguely defined as "annual to centennial" and would benefit from clearer specification. • The phenomena "storage/inventory" and "primary production" are empty. • Scientific application needs to be updated.
Figure 1: Spatial and temporal scales of phenomena	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure 1 does not give any additional information; it adds limited system-design clarity. • Needs for justification of the temporal/spatial scales
Table 3: Current 2017 observing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical coverage and footprint are not specified. • Under "supporting variables measured", only dissolved organic nitrogen (DON) is listed for repeat and fixed-point platforms. • Satellite remote sensing could be updated
Table 4: Future observing capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no clear roadmap for the integration of in situ dissolved organic carbon (DOC) proxies or BGC-ARGO observations. This section appears incomplete. • Validity of in-situ optical proxies need to be defined - these will be different in e.g., coastal and open ocean settings.
Figure 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure 2 does not add interpretive value beyond table 3.
Table 5: Data and information creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several links appear outdated and may be inactive; an update is required. • There is no dedicated global DOC climatology identified. • The satellite remote sensing section is largely incomplete. • Several new DOC repositories are available (open ocean and coastal)
Table 6: Links and references	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links and references should be updated. • Information about best practices and methodological guides need updating.
Glossary of terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define terminology and indicators following the GOOS vocabulary.
List of abbreviations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The terminology may need to be revised, as the current list dates from 2017.

General gaps:

- Information about the lead authors and contributors of each Spec Sheet is missing and should be provided.

3.9 Ocean Colour

BGC EOVS Ocean Colour Specification Sheet (Version: 2018.09.24)

GOOS+IOCCP (2017): https://www.ioccp.org/images/10FOO/BGC-EOV-Spec-Sheets_Aug-2017/EOV_Ocean-Colour_20180924.pdf

Table 9. Ocean Colour EOVS Spec Sheet section-by-section gap assessments

Section	Gap/ Comment
Background and justification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The background section is lengthy and mainly focuses on radiometry and sensor technology. It lacks a clear linkage reporting framework, the role of ocean colour in the SDGs and biodiversity conventions, and a stronger articulation of its relevance for policy and decision-making. The section would benefit from an updated description of the importance and impacts of ocean colour observations.
Table 1: EOVS information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is no clarification on mandatory/optional inputs.
Table 2: Requirement's settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The only Spec Sheet that refers to GOOS themes in table 2. Uncertainty requirements for the calcification phenomena are missing. The uncertainty values provided are not explained; there is no indication of how they were calculated or references supporting them.
Figure 1: Spatial and temporal scales of phenomena	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This figure does not provide any additional information and adds limited clarity regarding the observing system design.
Table 3: Current 2017 observing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reporting mechanisms and governance pathways are not described.
Table 4: Future observing capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some fields related to moored fixed-points and tower fixed-point observatories are blank and require revision.
Figure 2: Spatial and temporal observation scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Figure 2 does not add interpretive value beyond table 3.
Table 5: Data and information creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Several links appear outdated and may no longer be active; they should be reviewed and updated. References to regional data products are missing and should be included.
Table 6: Links and references	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Links and references should be updated.
Glossary of terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The current terminology list dates from 2017 and may require revision to reflect updated conventions.
List of abbreviations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The terminology may need to be revised, as the current list dates from 2017.

General gaps:

- Information about the lead authors and contributors of each Spec Sheets is missing and should be provided.

4 Priority revision needs

While the previous sections provide a detailed description of the gaps identified for each EOVS Spec Sheet, several cross-cutting issues emerge that should be prioritized in the revision process. These can be grouped into three categories: structural gaps (affecting all Spec Sheets), key scientific gaps (related to observing requirements), and secondary improvements (that would enhance usability and clarity).

4.1 Structural gaps

The assessment shows that several structural limitations occur consistently across most EOVS Spec Sheets. The current document does not clearly describe the full observing value chain linking measurements to final information products. Future revisions should clarify the relationship between observing platforms, measurements techniques, data management systems, synthesis products and indicators. Furthermore, improvements in guidance on metadata standards, FAIR principles, updated references and links to community standards and best practices are needed.

Inconsistencies between tables and figures introduce redundancy and reduce clarity. A harmonized Spec Sheet template should therefore be adopted for all EOVSs.

4.2 Key scientific gaps: Uncertainty and detectability requirements

One of the most critical gaps concerns the definition of uncertainty and detectability requirements. Without this information, Spec Sheets cannot function as operational observing guidance, because observing system designers cannot determine the level of accuracy/calibration required to detect specific phenomena. Future revisions should include explicit information about uncertainty, thresholds, drift tolerance and calibration requirements (such as the use of reference material).

4.3 Secondary improvements

In addition to these priority issues, additional improvements would increase the usability of the Spec Sheets. These include clearer definition of spatial/vertical coverage requirements, updates reflecting technological developments since 2017, stronger links to international observing frameworks such as GOOS, GCOS, and WMO RRR. By addressing these issues, clarity and operational usefulness for long-term practical uses will be improved.

5 Conclusions

The review of the existing BGC EOVS Spec Sheets reveals a set of recurring gaps that, taken together, limit their usefulness as operational reference documents. Addressing these in a coordinated revision is both necessary and timely.

At the structural level, inconsistencies in how tables and figures are organized introduce redundancy and ambiguity for the users. Key parameters such as vertical coverage (surface versus full-depth observations) are not consistently specified across EOVSs, and information about data flow and

management is largely absent. Spec Sheets should clearly describe the full observing value chain, from requirement setting through observing coordination to data delivery and products.

Alignment with international and regional observing and climate monitoring frameworks, also needs work. The number and definition of the BGC variable differs between GOOS and GCOS: GOOS defines nine BGC EOVs while GCOS identifies six BGC ocean ECVs. The current documents do not explain these differences or flag which EOVs are also designated as ECVs, even though this distinction might carry real implications for observing priorities and reporting obligations. This should be made explicit. The six GCOS ECVs are Dissolved Oxygen Concentration, Nutrients (Silicate, Phosphate, Nitrate), Inorganic Carbon (Total Alkalinity (TA), Total Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC), partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂)), Transient Tracers, nitrous oxide N₂O (interior ocean nitrous oxide N₂O, N₂O air-sea flux) and Ocean Colour (see GCOS, 2025). Future Spec Sheets should clearly identify which EOVs carry ECV status and explain what that means in practice.

Beyond GOOS-GCOS, the Spec Sheets should more explicitly connect BGC observations to the GOOS delivery areas: Climate (UN, Paris agreement), operational services (disaster risk reduction, weather forecasting and hazard warnings, IMO), ocean health (global biodiversity framework, plastic treaty, biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction, SDG14/ sustainable ocean management) to better highlight the societal relevance and the value of ocean observations. Making these links visible strengthens the case for sustained investment and helps users understand the broader relevance of what they are measuring.

On data management, the current Spec Sheets provide very restricted guidance and need significant update and improvement. FAIR data principles are not well addressed, and information on metadata standards, data access and data submission pipelines are often limited or missing. Revised Spec Sheets should provide clear guidance on data repositories, data schemes, and data submission workflows to support interoperability at the global scale.

Related to this, integration with community standards and best practices is needed (e.g., OBPS). More explicit links to standardized protocols and standard operating procedures would improve consistency and make it easier for new contributors to engage correctly from the start. Addressing these revisions would improve clarity and usability, strengthen alignment with international observing frameworks, and support the long-term implementation and coordination of BGC EOVs.

6 References

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